

COMPARISON OF VIDEO CONFERENCE AND FACE TO FACE MENTORING SERVICES ON ADVISEES' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS

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Abstract:

The aim of the research is to compare the impacts of mentoring services, delivered face to face and video conference on advisees' academic achievements. Mentoring services, made up with two different instruments, were administered to a group of advisees, composed of 32 university students. In the research, the multiple-choice achievement test, which consisted of thirty, 5-point Likert items, was utilized in order to determine advisees' academic achievements.

Keywords: mentoring, face to face, video conference, advisee, academic achievements

Introduction

Mentoring is defined in general as maximizing individuals' learning potentials, improving their skills, increasing their performances, and supporting and encouraging them to become the person they want to be. Adams and Crews (2004) indicate that telementoring is the electronic version of mentoring. Single & Muller (1999) define telementoring as a relationship between a more senior individual (mentor) and a lesser skilled or experienced individual (advisee) primarily using electronic communications, and that is intended to grow the skills, knowledge, confidence and cultural understanding of the advisee to help him or her to succeed. O'Neill (2000), on the other hand, defines telementoring as the use of telecommunication technologies to support a mentoring relationship when a face-to-face relationship would be impractical. Mentoring is conducted in two categories (Dorman, 2001; American School Health Association, 2001; Hansman, 2002, Perez and Dorman, 2001) as face to face and tele-

mentoring in which using advanced technology. The aim of the research is the comparison of the impacts of two different mentoring practices on student achievement which are formed on the basis of face to face and video conferencing.

Method, data collection tools

The advisee group of the research consists of 32 students who take the course "Instructional design". The first group, where face to face advising was used between the advisee and the mentor, is composed of 16 students; the second group where video conference was used is composed of 16 students. Students in these groups received mentoring service in addition to their ordinary education. Necessary information was given to the mentors prior to the research about the content and the subject of the research, and the things that need to be done throughout the research. Mentoring services were performed for four weeks. The validity and reliability studies of the achievement test of the research were conducted in line with the evidence obtained from Trochim (2001) and Miles and Huberman (1994). The achievement test was prepared with 5-point Likert scale and consists of 30 items. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is .88. Upon completion of the training and participation, the achievement test was applied to the groups as the final test.

Findings

Comparison of the achievement scores taken from pre-test: Table 1 demonstrates the Mann-Whitney U. test results of the scores taken from Pretest by the groups, in which different mentoring instruments are used.

Table 1: Mann-Whitney U. test results of the scores taken from Pretest by the groups

Groups	n	Mean Rank	$\bar{x}$	p
Group 1 st	14	23,38	4,54	,32
Group 2 nd	18	24,19		

Mann-Whitney U test analysis results demonstrated in Table 1 indicate that there is not any significant difference between the achievement scores taken in the Pretest; by the 1st group where face to face advising, by the 2nd group where video conference, was used:

$$[(\chi^2) = .32, p > .05].$$

Comparison of the achievement scores taken from post-test: Table 2 demonstrates the Mann-Whitney U. test results of the scores taken from post-test by the groups, in which different mentoring instruments are used.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney U. test results of the scores taken from Posttest by the groups

Groups	n	Mean Rank	χ^2	p
Group1 st	14	28,81	5,58	.36
Group2 nd	18	27,44		

Mann-Whitney U test analysis results demonstrated in Table 2 indicate that there is not any significant difference between the achievement scores taken in the Posttest; by the 1st group where face to face advising , by the 2nd group where video conference, was used:

$$[(\chi^2) = .36, p > .05]$$

Despite several limitations such as low number of students in study groups, the subject worked on, and limited mentoring durations, research findings demonstrate that advisee achievement does not differ significantly according to whether the mentoring services are provided through video conference and face to face.

Conclusion

Findings of the current study, despite its limitations, demonstrate that mentoring services created by using video conferencing and face to face advising do not significantly differentiate advisees' academic achievement. The reason no significant difference was found between research groups in terms of academic achievement might be the fact that all instruments have the same communicational impact on achievement; no matter they are used over the media or face to face.

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